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THERMAL AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF FLAX YARNS MODIFIED WITH GRAPHENE OXIDE

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Introduction

Context

- Materials
- Thermal Stability of GO Treated Flax Fibres
- Tensile Stiffness and Strength of Technical Fibres
- Effect of GO on Flax / Epoxy Interfacial Shear Strength
- Tensile Properties of Flax / Epoxy Vs. Flax – GO/ Epoxy UD Composites

OBJECTIVE

Improved thermal stability of GO modified flax fibres at processing temperatures over 200 °C, which is typical for thermoplastic resins is targeted. Based on the chemical functional groups on GO (e.g., OH), better flax/epoxy affinity is aimed. It is expected that enhanced interfacial shear strength and toughness will alter tensile strength and stiffness of GO modified flax – epoxy composites.

Materials

- 1.2 wt% Graphene Oxide (GO) aqueous dispersion

The oxidation step of graphite flakes is based on Hummers and Offeman, 1957 in presence of:
98% H_2SO_4 , NaNO_3 , KMnO_4

Graphite

Hummers method

Sonication

Water evaporation

Materials

- Flax bundles and technical fibres were extracted from non-crimp flax fabric with 300 gsm provided by Bcomp
- GO treated Flax fibre bundles were achieved by immersing as received flax bundles into the 1.2 wt% GO aqueous dispersion for 24 hr. GO modified bundles dried 2 hr at 80 °C and 48 hr at 60 °C

Resin Systems:

- EPON 828 epoxy with a low molecular weight polyoxypropylene diamine hardener. This resin used for the droplet deposition on technical fibres. Droplets were cured at 60 °C for 2hr and 1 hr at 150 °C
- Epikote 828 LVEL with Dytek DCH-99 (amin) hardener: used for the production of impregnated fibre bundle test and flax – epoxy tensile test samples. Samples were cured at 150 °C for 2 hr

Thermal Stability of GO Treated Flax Fibres

Isothermal TGA Results

- TGA results suggest improved thermal stability by GO treatment

- TGA scans are performed with Netzsch TG209F3. Heating rate from 30 °C to the isothermal range is 10 °C/min.

Tensile Stiffness and Strength of Technical Fibres

- Tensile test coupons are made based on Impregnated Fibre Bundle Test (IFBT)
- Tensile stiffness and the strength of technical flax fibres are back-calculated based on the rule of mixture

$$V_f = \frac{m_f / \rho_f}{V_c} \quad E_f = \frac{E_c - E_m(1 - V_f)}{V_f} \quad \sigma_{uf} = \frac{\sigma_c - \sigma_m(1 - V_f)}{V_f}$$

- To calculate the mass of flax bundles required to achieve 40% fibre volume fraction with epoxy resin:

Mf = fibre volume fraction * volume of composite * density of fibres

$$M_f = 0.4 * (20 \text{ cm} * 0.2 \text{ cm} * 1 \text{ cm}) * 1.35 \text{ [g/cm}^3] = 2.16 \text{ gr}$$

- Resin system is Epikot 828 LVEL /amine

Tensile modulus: 2.7 GPa

Tensile strength: 70 MPa

Strain at failure: 4%

Curing cycle: 2 hr at 150 °C

IFBT molds

Tensile Stiffness and Strength of Technical Fibres

$$V_f = \frac{m_f / \rho_f}{V_c} \quad E_f = \frac{E_c - E_m(1 - V_f)}{V_f} \quad \sigma_{uf} = \frac{\sigma_c - \sigma_m(1 - V_f)}{V_f}$$

*Back calculated properties

Material	$E_{0.1\%}$ GPa*	$E_{0.3-0.5\%}$ GPa*	Tensile Strength MPa*
Flax	48 ± 5	31 ± 3	546 ± 54
Flax - GO	54 ± 2	36 ± 1	592 ± 22
Flax 10 min at 240 °C	47 ± 2	34 ± 2	234 ± 34
Flax - GO 10 min at 240 °C	47 ± 2	34 ± 1	267 ± 17

- Tensile strength of technical fibres is sensitive to heat treatment above 200 °C
- The decline in the tensile stiffness of fibres is rather slight compared to the strength
- The tensile stiffness and strength of technical flax fibres are in the same range as GO modified flax fibre

Effect of GO on the Interfacial Shear Strength of Flax - Epoxy

$$\tau_{av} = F / \pi DL$$

$$F = \tau_{av}A + \underbrace{\mu 2F \cot \frac{\theta}{\pi}}_{(I)}$$

F: Debonding load recorded by the load cell

A: Embedded area

I: Extra force required to debond the droplet caused by compressive forces

- The average diameter of technical flax fibres for microbond test: 21 μm
- The average embedded length: 87 μm

- GO treatment improves the apparent shear strength of flax-epoxy by **43%**

Effect of GO on the Tensile Stiffness and Strength of Flax – Epoxy UD Composites

Composite	Matrix	E_m GPa	σ_m MPa	V_f %	$E_{f0.1\%}$ GPa	$E_{f0.3-0.5\%}$ GPa	σ_f MPa
Flax epoxy	Epikote 828 LVEL	2.7	70	40	21 ± 2	14 ± 1	260 ± 21
Flax - GO - epoxy	Epikote 828 LVEL	2.7	70	40	23 ± 1	16 ± 1	279 ± 9

- Tensile fracture surface of flax- epoxy:
Cracks propagate along the fibre/loading direction

- Tensile fracture surface of GO modified flax - epoxy:
GO modified samples fail transverse to the fibre direction. GO modified flax epoxy interphase do no allow crack propagation alongside the sample. This can be related to the [improvement in the interfacial strength/toughness at micro-scale](#).

Conclusion

- TGA results suggest improved thermal stability of GO treated flax fibres
- Tensile stiffness and strength of technical flax fibres are consistent with and without GO treatments
- Although TGA results promise better thermal stability over 200 °C with GO modified technical flax fibres, tensile stiffness and strength of the heat treated technical flax fibres for 10 min at 240 °C are in the same range as Flax - GO
- GO treatment of technical flax fibres enhance the apparent interfacial shear strength by 43%
- Tensile stiffness and strength of GO modified flax - epoxy composites are 9% and 7% higher than flax - epoxy composite thanks to the improved interfacial shear strength at the microscale